

COMPRESSION PERFORMANCES OF CONCRETE CYLINDERS CONFINED BY FLAX FIBER BASED FRP COMPOSITES

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Abstract

In the present paper, a flax fabric reinforced epoxy composites was applied to confine concrete cylinders for enhancement of the compression performances of the cylinders. Flax fiber reinforced epoxy composites were prepared and tested on their tensile properties. It was found that the flax reinforced composites in weft or warp directions show remarkable difference in the tensile properties. Compared to the unidirectional basalt fiber reinforced epoxy system, the flax based fiber reinforced polymer (FFRP) composites exhibited relatively lower tensile strength and modulus, but higher elongation at break, and the tensile strain ~ stress curves deviate from linearity. The compression strength and axial stain of the concrete cylinders confined with FFRPs were enhanced significantly. The FFRP confined concrete cylinders have much higher failure strain than those with basalt fiber reinforced polymer systems. The results indicated that the flax fabric can be used to confine concrete cylinders effectively.

1 Introduction

In recent years, natural fiber reinforcements as alternatives to glass or carbon fibers have been widely used in automobile, decoration and the other industry fields, due to the advantages such as low density, renewable resource usage, low cost, biodegradability etc. [1]. Among them, flax fiber is an attractive candidate because of their relatively higher mechanical properties [2]. Natural fibers have special chemical structures and their tensile stress ~ strain curves do not show linear characteristics. In view of this, the structures reinforced or strengthened with natural fibers are endowed with special performances.

As known, the structural ductility and carrying capacity of a concrete cylinder (or column) can be

enhanced effectively through confinement by glass- or carbon-fiber reinforced FRP composites [3]. In the present study, flax fabric reinforced epoxy wet layups were applied to confine plain concrete cylinders. The compression behaviors of the confined and un-confined concrete cylinders were tested. The effects of flax fabric layers, fiber orientation of the fabric were investigated.

The aim of the study is to understand the compression performances of the concrete cylinders confined with flax fiber reinforced FRP (FFRP) sheets. The effectiveness of confinement by FFRP and basalt fiber reinforced FRPs were compared. The study will demonstrate the feasibility of the natural fiber reinforced FRPs used in structural strengthening, rehabilitation and upgrading.

2 Experimental

2.1 Raw materials

A bi-directional flax fabric woven in warp and weft directions was supplied by Changli Textile Company (Harbin, China). The density of the flax fabric is 1.5 g/mm². The normalized thickness is 0.16 mm. A basalt fabric, supplied by Sichuan Aerospace Tuoxin Basalt Fiber Co. (Chengdu, Sichuan), was used for a comparison. The tensile strength, modulus and elongation at break of the basalt fibers are reported as 2.7 GPa, 85.36 GPa and 3.7%, respectively.

An epoxy system used for FRP composites is supplied by Fyfe Co. (California, USA). The basic properties of the resin are listed in Table 1.

2.2 Preparation and mechanical test of NFRP composite samples

Two-layer of flax fabric reinforced epoxy coupons were made by hand wet layup process. The fiber directions are carefully controlled, and the fiber

directions of the two layers of fabric are parallel. Based on the fiber direction, two kind of tensile samples were cut, one in warp direction and the other in weft direction. The width and length of the tensile samples are 15mm x 250mm.

The tensile properties were tested according to ASTM D 3039 (Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials), with an electronic universal tensile testing machine (WDW100D, Jinan Shijin Company, Jinan, China). The tensile rate is set as 2 mm/s with the gauge length of 150 mm.

2.2 Preparation and compression test of NFRP confined concrete cylinders

The flax fabric was wrapped on the concrete cylinders by hand wet layup process with the epoxy resin system (see in Table 1). Two layers of carbon fiber sheets wrapped on the ends of the flax fiber confined cylinders with 5 mm width to avoid the end damage. After the solidification of the epoxy resin, six strain gauges were pasted on the surface of the strengthened cylinder in the middle region. The wrapped concrete cylinder is shown in Figure 1. To measure the displacement of the middle part during compression, four LVDTs (linear voltage differential transducer) were applied as shown in Figure 2.

In this paper, the cylinders wrapped with the flax fabric in warp direction are marked as N, followed by the number of fabric layers. NV represents the cylinders confined with the fabric in weft direction. Two repeat samples were conducted for each case. The cylinders were tested with a 500T hydraulically operated machine with the load speed of 0.25 MPa/s.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Tensile properties of FFRPs

Figure 3 presents the tensile strain ~ stress curves of the pure epoxy resin, BFRP and FFRPs in weft and warp directions. Table 2 summarized the tensile strength, modulus and elongation at break of the mentioned samples.

As shown, the NFRP coupons in warp direction exhibited lower strength and modulus, but higher elongation than that in weft direction. This is because the yarns in warp direction are waved rather than being straight. Under tension, therefore, the waved fibers are

stretched, and thus the NFRP samples exhibit much higher elongation at break. Due to the same reason, the samples show lower strength and modulus. In addition, compared to the unidirectional BFRP samples, the bidirectional NFRP samples show much lower strength and modulus than BFRP. This can be attributed to the low mechanical property of the flax fabric, low fiber volume content, and the incompatibility between the polar fiber and nonpolar resin.

It is worth noting that the strain ~ stress curves of the FFRP samples differ from the linearity. As indicated by the second stage (see in Figure 3), the modulus shows much reduced.

Figure 4 shows the SEM micrograph of the transverse section of NFRP after tension failure. There is few resins attached on the fiber surfaces, indicating the weak bonding between the flax fiber and the epoxy resin matrix.

3.2 Compression properties of the confined concrete cylinders

As shown in Figure 5, strengthened cylinders under compression, similar to the synthetic fibers wrapped concrete cylinders, the stress - strain curves of the FFRP strengthened cylinders exhibits two stages. The tangent slope of stress-strain curve of FFRP strengthened cylinder of the first stage is almost the same as the plain and the synthetic fiber confined concrete cylinders.

According to ACI 440.2R-08 (Guide for the Design and Construction of Externally Bonded FRP Systems for Strengthening Concrete Structures), the shape of the compression curve of the FFRP confined cylinder is closed to the heavily confined-softening one's. Though the conclusion is drawn by the synthetic fiber based composites, the invariable stress with increasing strain at the second stage suggested that the FFRP in hoop direction cannot provide enough confinement to the concrete cylinders. However, it is worth noting, the FFRP confined cylinders exhibits much higher deformation in the hoop directions, especially for the cylinders confined with FFRPs in warp direction.

As shown in Figure 6, the failure mode of FFRP confined cylinders is different from other unidirectional materials reinforced ones. The wrapped NFRPs break in a straight line both in warp and weft directions. These properties of woven fabric were explained as "knee phenomenon" [4]. This means that the locally induced moment reduces loading capacity

and transverse cracking gives rise to successive failure process. For FFRP in warp, the existence of yarn in weft direction deteriorates the tensile properties since the weft fibers can be considered as flaws. The warp fibers show the similar effect for the mechanical properties of FFRPs in weft. Consequently, the rupture of structure happens along the vertical yarns as shown in Figure 6.

The improvement of the wrapped concrete cylinders in compression strength can be expressed as following equations [5]:

$$\frac{f_{cu}}{f_{co}} = 1 + k_1 \frac{f_{l,a}}{f_{co}} \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{cu}}{\varepsilon_{co}} = 1 + k_2 \frac{f_{l,a}}{f_{co}} \quad (1b)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are defined as the coefficient of confinement and general considered as 3.3 for CFRP confined concrete, f_{cu} , f_{co} , ε_{cu} , ε_{co} and $f_{l,a}$ stand for the ultimate stress/strain of the confined/unconfined cylinders and actual confinement respectively. The equation to calculate $f_{l,a}$ recommended by Lam and Teng [3] with the equation below:

$$f_{l,a} = \frac{2E_{frp}t\varepsilon_{h,rupt}}{d} \quad (2)$$

Where E_{frp} , $\varepsilon_{h,rupt}$, t are the mean modulus, ultimate stress and thickness of the wrapped materials, d is the diameter of the cylinder.

There is another equation can be adopted to calculate $f_{l,a}$:

$$f_{l,a} = \frac{2f_{frp}t}{d} \quad (3)$$

where $f_{l,a}$ is the tensile strength of the wrapped FRP composites which is not equal to $E_{frp}t$ for synthetic fiber materials. That is because the rupture stress of FRP jacket cannot reach the ultimate strength of coupon test. The conclusion was drawn by Lam & Teng [5] to confirm the actual confinement of FRP wrapped concrete.

However, the results of coupon test reveal that the constitutive relationship of FFRP composite is different from CFRP or other synthetic fiber bonded FRP with linear properties. The rupture stress of the wrapped FRPs cannot reach the ultimate strength in eventual failure, which was found and confirmed by large rupture strain materials.

As shown in Figure 5, the compression stress-strain curves have two-stages. In the second stage, the

stress almost level off with the increase of the strain. That means the axial stress of strengthened cylinder achieves the ultimate strength and the strain may not reach the ultimate strain. In view of this, the appropriate calculation of the hoop confinement should use the ultimate stress rather than the strain.

Besides, the accurate ultimate hoop strain is hard to get as reported frequently [6-8]. For FFRP strengthened cylinder in the present paper, the expression of $f_{l,a}$ is calculated following Eq. 3.

As shown in Figure 7(a), the coefficient of confinement (k_1 , calculated following Eq.1(a)) of FFRP confined cylinder is larger than the results of prior researches which are mostly 3 to 4. In the present study, k_1 of BFRP is 5.12, the value is a little larger than prior researches, yet less than the FFRP. The effective confinement of the natural fabric is larger than synthetic fabric. The probable reason is that the elastic modulus of FFRP is much lower than the synthetic fiber reinforced FRPs. Consequently, it is possible to coordinate the deformation of the wrapped FFRPs and confined concrete. At the same time, the large ultimate strain of FFRP improves the ductility of strengthened cylinder.

As the coupon testes showed that the tensile properties of FFRP in weft direction are better than that in warp, the confinement effect of the NFRPs in weft direction are larger than weft.

As shown in Table 3 and Figure 7(b), the enhancement of the ultimate stress (k_2 , calculated by Eq.1(b)) has no regular pattern with $f_{l,a}$ as expected. This is because the ultimate elongation of FFRP is much larger than the deformation capacity of the concrete. The concrete in the core breaks before the wrapped FFRP reaches the ultimate strain.

Another reason to account the characteristic of FFRP in axial ultimate strain is the efficiency in hoop deformation of wrapped material. For conventional FRP jacket, the secant modulus from coupon test is constant. The confinement of FRP can be calculated with modulus as a fixed value. That method was adopted for linear stress-strain materials and was found not suitable for FRPs with large deformability. Thus the efficiency of axial ultimate strain to rupture strain from coupon test is shown in Table 4, and it is much smaller than other LRS synthetic materials.

4 Conclusions

Flax fabrics reinforced FRPs show different tensile behaviors in weft or warp directions. Compared to the unidirectional BFRP composite, FFRPs exhibited lower tensile strength and modulus, but higher elongation at break. The compressive strength and axial stain of the concrete cylinders confined with FFRPs were enhanced significantly. The FFRP confined concrete cylinders have much higher failure strain than those with BFRPs.

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Table 1 The basic properties of epoxy resin used in the NFRP

Basic property	Index given by the producer
Color	≤90 Pt-Co
Epoxy Equiv	184-200 g/mol
Hydrolyzable Chlorine	≤0.5 %
Inorganic Chlorine	≤0.018 %
Volatile (150°C,40 min)	≤0.8 %
Viscosity (25 °C)	7000-18000 mPa·s

Table 2 Tensile properties of resin, FFRPs and BFRP composites.

	Tensile strength σ (MPa)	Modulus E _{frp} (GPa)	Thickness t (mm)	Elongation at break ϵ_u (%)
Resin	83.61	3.03	3.5	4.26
FFRP in Warp	185	13.6	0.32	4.06
FFRP in Weft	349.45	19.7	0.32	2.35
BFRP	793.3	31.4	0.4	2.4

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Table 3 The compressive behavior of concrete cylinders wrapped with different types of FRPs.

	F_{cu} (MPa)	k	E_o (GPa)	ε_{cu}
Plain	19.06	/	21.6	0.002
N4	28.15	6.89	12.9	0.018
N8	37.63	7.03	15.48	0.024
N12	48.06	7.32	22.9	0.024
BFRP	37.83	4.44	27.3	0.013
NV4	33.47	5.46	13.54	0.012
NV8	33.47	5.46	13.54	0.012

Table 4 Rupture strain of the FRP sheet confined cylinders versus rupture strain of FRP coupons

FRP type	Coupon rupture strain	Jacket rupture strain	Efficiency factor
N4		0.0184	0.453
N8	0.0406	0.0241	0.593
N12		0.0237	0.583
BFRP	0.0176	0.0130	0.738
NV4		0.0120	0.510
NV8	0.0235	0.0160	0.681

Fig. 1. Concrete cylinders wrapped with NFRP sheets. Note: the ends were extra strengthened with CFRP.

Fig. 2. Compression testing setup of NFR confined concrete cylinder.

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Fig. 3. Tensile strain ~ stress curves of FFRP, BFRP and resin.

Figure 4 SEM photos of fracture surface of FFRP tensile fracture surfaces.

Fig.5. The axial strain ~ stress curves of plain and confined concrete cylinders during compression. Note, N4, N8 and N12 indicate 4, 8 and 12 layers of FFRPs were used.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Failure mode of NFRP strengthened concrete in warp direction (a) and weft direction (b)

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(a)

Fig. 7. Evaluation of the confinement effect in strength (a) and strain (b) of FRPs.